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IGG4-RELATED DISEASES IN THE BACKGROUND OF DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation. *IgG4-related disease (IgG4-CD) is characterized by the appearance of tumor-like foci in one or more organs, occurring synchronously or metachronously, due to fibroinflammatory changes with hypersecretion of immunoglobulin G subclass 4 (IgG4) in tissues and/or serum. Diabetes mellitus (DM) develops in 43–68% of patients with IgG4-related pancreatitis. Diabetes in the setting of IgG4-SD can be caused by both damage to the endocrine pancreas and the use of glucocorticosteroids, but its course is moderate, with a rare need for insulin therapy. In both cases, the use of genetic engineering biological therapy with rituximab may be accompanied by an improvement in carbohydrate metabolism. This article presents a clinical observation of the course of diabetes and the characteristics of the need for antidiabetic therapy over a period of 1.5 years in a patient receiving treatment for IgG4-CD.*

KEYWORDS: *IgG4-related disease; diabetes; autoimmune pancreatitis; glucocorticoids; rituximab*

IGG4-АССОЦИИРОВАННЫЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ НА ФОНЕ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА

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***Аннотация.** IgG4-ассоциированное заболевание (IgG4-CD) характеризуется появлением опухолеподобных очагов в одном или нескольких органах, протекающих синхронно или метакронно, вследствие фибровоспалительных изменений с гиперсекрецией иммуноглобулина G подкласса 4 (IgG4) в тканях и/или сыворотке крови. Сахарный диабет (СД) развивается у 43–68% больных IgG4-ассоциированным панкреатитом. Сахарный диабет на фоне IgG4-SD может быть обусловлен как поражением эндокринной системы поджелудочной железы, так и применением глюкокортикостероидов, но течение его умеренное, с редкой необходимостью инсулинотерапии. В обоих случаях применение генно-инженерной биологической терапии ритуксимабом может сопровождаться улучшением углеводного обмена. В статье представлены клиническое наблюдение течения сахарного диабета и особенности необходимости антидиабетической терапии на протяжении 1,5 лет у пациента, получающего лечение по поводу IgG4-CD.*

Ключевые слова: IgG4-ассоциированные заболевания; диабет; аутоиммунный панкреатит; глюкокортикоиды; ритуксимаб.

Introduction. IgG4-related disease (IgG4-S3) is an immune-mediated chronic systemic disease characterized by the appearance of tumor-like foci in one or more organs, occurring synchronously or metachronously, due to fibroinflammatory changes with hypersecretion of immunoglobulin G of the 4th subclass (IgG4) in tissues and/or blood serum [1]. Endocrine manifestations of IgG4-CD include pancreatitis with the development of diabetes mellitus (DM), as well as Riedel's fibrosing thyroiditis and lymphocytic hypophysitis. Autoimmune pancreatitis within the framework of IgG4-C3 (AIP type 1) is often accompanied by damage to other target organs with the development of sialadenitis, biliary stenosis, interstitial lung disease, orbital pseudotumor, nephritis, etc. In such cases, a biopsy of these organs with the detection of characteristic histological signs of the disease, such as moiré-like fibrosis, obliterating phlebitis, lymphoplasmacytic infiltration, makes it possible to verify the diagnosis. Similar histological changes can be detected in the tissues of the pancreas, but its biopsy is not performed in routine clinical practice for IgG4-C3 [2]. In the early stages of the disease, clinical symptoms may be absent. As the disease progresses, signs of cholestasis appear, which forms when the pancreas compresses the common bile duct, as well as such nonspecific clinical manifestations as mild or moderate

abdominal pain, general fatigue, and weight loss. In 17% of patients, the disease may be asymptomatic [3]. In such cases, damage to the pancreas may be an incidental finding during instrumental examination of the abdominal organs. AIP type 1 is characterized by a diffuse increase in the size of the pancreas with the formation of a “sausage-shaped appearance”, a rectangular shape at the tail (“clipped tail sign”). Involvement of the main duct of the gland is also noted with damage to more than 1/3 of its length in one fragment or in the form of a multifocal lesion with alternating areas of narrowing or disappearance of the duct without previous dilatation or other signs of obstructive pancreatitis [4]. Laboratory data show signs of cholestasis, increased levels of total protein and gammaglobulins, IgG4 in the blood, and increased ESR [5]. According to studies, diabetes develops among 43–68% of patients with IgG4-AIP, but its course is moderate, with a rare need for insulin therapy. Diabetes may be the first and only manifestation of type 1 AIP [6]. Glucocorticosteroids (GCS) are used as first-line drugs for the treatment of AIP type 1, and in fairly high doses - 0.6 mg/kg/day. Interestingly, during GCS therapy, a “paradoxical” effect of improving glycemic parameters may be observed [7]. This article describes the course of diabetes and changes in antidiabetic therapy over 1.5 years in a patient treated with IgG4-SD.

CASE DESCRIPTION The patient is a Caucasian man, 41 years old, who applied to the Federal State Budgetary Institution “Research Institute of Rheumatology named after. V.A. Nasonova” in October 2020 with complaints of severe general weakness, jaundice of the skin, diffuse skin itching, discomfort in the epigastrium, nausea, and weight loss of 26 kg since January 2020. Since 2017, he has noted the emergence and increase of general weakness and fatigue. In March 2019, attacks of hepatic colic appeared and he received symptomatic therapy. At the end of 2019, a hematologist diagnosed acquired hemophilia with deficiency of factors IX, XI, XII. Due to the absence of a specific hemorrhagic clinical picture, it is recommended to refrain from specific therapy. Also, at the end of 2019, swelling of the eyelids appeared in the morning. According to computed tomography (CT) of the orbits from March 2020, a massive enlargement of the lacrimal glands on both sides and hyperplastic polysinusitis was detected. In May 2020, an MRI of the abdominal cavity revealed a large hypodense formation in the pancreas with edema of the parapancreatic tissue, lymphadenopathy in the area of the parapancreatic tissue, and multiple low-density foci in both kidneys. The IgG4 value in the blood was 3 g/l (0.1–1.35 g/l). In August 2020, he applied for a correspondence consultation at the Federal State Budgetary Institution “NIIR named after. V.A. Nasonova”, the diagnosis was established: IgG4-S3

(autoimmune pancreatitis? dacryoadenitis, sialadenitis?). At the end of August 2020, with clinical manifestations of obstructive jaundice, the patient was hospitalized in a surgical hospital at his place of residence. Due to acquired hemophilia, surgical treatment was refused. A number of studies were completed in October 2020. According to positron emission tomography combined with CT (PET-CT): accumulation of a radiopharmaceutical (^{18}F -FDG) was recorded in the spleen, thickened lacrimal glands, and kidneys; totally in the enlarged pancreas; in the lymph nodes: cervical-supraclavicular, retromammary and axillary, mediastinal (upper paratracheal, preaortic at the level of the left main bronchus, bifurcation bronchopulmonary), hepatic hilum, common and external iliac on both sides. On a CT scan of the abdominal organs, attention is drawn to a diffuse increase in the size of the pancreas. As part of the differential diagnosis, lymphoproliferative disease was excluded, however, due to the atypical clinical picture (severe, extensive multiorgan damage), BCL2-negativity, the absence of mutations involving the BCL6/3q27, cMYC/8q24, BCL2/18q21 gene loci, the absence of B-cell clonality, the diagnosis of lymphoma was excluded. In October 2020, due to deterioration of his condition - severe general weakness, icteric skin, diffuse skin itching, feeling of discomfort in the epigastrium, nausea, weight loss (by 26 kg since January 2020), he was hospitalized in the hospital of the Federal State Budgetary Institution "NIIR named after. V.A. Nasonova" for verification of diagnosis and correction of therapy. During the examination: total bilirubin 285.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, direct bilirubin 274.51 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, alkaline phosphatase 214.0 U/L, fasting glucose 11.7 mmol/L (Table 1). Immunological blood test: rheumatoid factor - negative, IgG4 12.5 g/l (normal) Considering the severity of the condition, the active inflammatory process, insulin therapy was chosen for the initial treatment of diabetes: Glulisine 6 U 3 times a day, Glargine 20 U/day (Table 2). During subsequent hospitalizations in October-November, rituximab 500 mg was reintroduced intravenously. A total of 2000 mg of rituximab was administered, and pulse therapy with methylprednisolone was performed twice (250 mg with a gradual reduction in the dose of methylprednisolone, first to 24 mg/day, then 22 mg /day for 1 month). Subsequently, Glimepiride 4 mg/day, Linagliptin 5 mg/day were used as antidiabetic therapy in October 2020; in December 2020, the dose of methylprednisolone was reduced to 12 mg. To correct hyperglycemia, he was again transferred to Glulisine 6 U 3 times / day, Glargine 12 U / day. In December 2020, he was hospitalized at the NIIR. Before admission to the hospital, the patient was objectively noted to have swelling of the feet, and subsequently a decrease in pastosity. The occurrence of this condition was regarded as an effect

of the therapy. Since December 2020, over the course of several weeks, positive dynamics of edema have been noted, as well as a decrease in the intensity of jaundice, and an improvement in overall well-being. PET-CT was performed in March 2021. Compared with PET-CT from October 2020, pronounced positive dynamics were observed in the form of resorption of all previously determined changes in the lymph nodes, lacrimal glands, pancreas, liver, kidneys, prostate gland, seminal vesicles, and resolution of pericardial effusion. In March 2021, he was hospitalized at the Research Institute of Rheumatology for the planned administration of rituximab 500 mg, pulse therapy with methylprednisolone 250 mg followed by methylprednisolone 1 mg/day, a change in hypoglycemic therapy - a reduction in insulin doses - Glargine 7 U 1 r/day, Actrapid 5 U 2 times a day, and in December 2021 he was hospitalized again for the planned administration of rituximab 500 mg. DM therapy was changed - insulin was canceled and Ipragliflozin 50 mg/day was prescribed. Currently, therapy with long-acting metformin 500 mg/day is being carried out with full achievement of individual glycemic targets. The choice of glucose-lowering therapy was made based on the severity of the patient's condition, and subsequently, at the outpatient stage, based on the indicators of carbohydrate metabolism and medications available for obtaining. Subsequently, Glimpiride 4 mg/day, Linagliptin 5 mg/day were used as antidiabetic therapy in October 2020; in December 2020, the dose of methylprednisolone was reduced to 12 mg.

CONCLUSION. Diabetes developing against the background of IgG4-D3 can be caused by both damage to the endocrine part of the pancreas and the use of corticosteroids. In both cases, the use of genetic engineering biological therapy with rituximab may be accompanied by an improvement in carbohydrate metabolism, either due to a reduction in the dose of GCS, or against the background of regression of pancreatitis. Features of the course of diabetes in patients with IgG4-CD require further study with the study of larger samples of patients.

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